

PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE USE OF HUMAN RESOURCES.

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Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotini boshqarishda inson resurslaridan foydalanishning psixologik xususiyatlari, boshqaruvchilar va xodimlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqalarni tushunish, motivatsiya, kommunikatsiya, qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'zlashtirish va stress bilan boshqarish kabi muhim aspektlarga bog'liqdir.

Bu xususiyatlar, boshqaruvchilar uchun muhimdir, chunki ularga xodimlarni ilg'or ish bilan qiziqtirish, ularga maqsadlarni tushunish va ularga qanday qilib o'zlashtirish kerakligini tushunishlari kerak. Boshqaruvchilar, xodimlar bilan samarali kommunikatsiya o'rnatilgan holda o'zaro ishbilarmonlik va maqsadlarga yo'naltirilgan aloqalarni rivojlantirishlari kerak. Qo'llab-quvvatlash, xodimlarni bir-biriga yordam berish, o'zaro fikr almashish va jamoatchilikni oshirishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Rag'batlantirish, ilg'or ish, maqsadlarni tushunish, energiya, iste'dod, qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'zaro fikr almashish, maqsadlarga yo'naltirilgan kommunikatsiya, o'zaro ishbilarmonlik, o'zaro qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'zaro yordam.

Abstract: the management of the psychological characteristics of a preschool educational organization in human resource management depend on the interactions between the manager and employees important aspects such as understanding, motivation, communication, support, master, professional, and stress management.

Important characteristics are the highway manager for advanced work because they need to engage employees in the make I understand the goals, how to motivate and understand the I have. The developer must mutual business acumen manager and goal-oriented relationships with employees through effective communication. Allows support to employees to help each other, share, and build community.

Keywords: Motivation, advanced work, understanding the goal of energy, talent, support the idea of exchange, goal-oriented communication, mutual business, mutual respect 'support, mutual aid.

Аннотация: Психологические особенности управления человеческими ресурсами в управлении дошкольной образовательной организацией зависят от таких важных аспектов, как понимание взаимодействий руководителей и сотрудников, мотивация, коммуникация, поддержка, мастерство, управление стрессом.

Эти характеристики важны для менеджеров, потому что им необходимо вовлекать сотрудников в продвинутую работу, заставляя их понимать цели и понимать, как их мотивировать. Менеджеры должны развивать взаимную деловую хватку и целеустремленные отношения с сотрудниками посредством эффективного

общения. Поддержка позволяет сотрудникам помогать друг другу, делиться идеями и создавать сообщество.

Ключевые слова: Мотивация, опережающая работа, понимание целей, энергия, талант, поддержка, обмен идеями, целеустремленное общение, взаимное дело, взаимоуважение, поддержка, взаимопомощь.

Access

Pre-school education institutions in the management of human resources are analyzed in this article is about the use of psychological qualities. Human resources, organization and is important for the implementation, but they also know the importance and difficulty requires. In the article, the importance of human resources and difficulty is observed, psychological characteristics, motivation and the importance of the character major target to adapters explained. Communication, active within the creative, the higher the stress management in public and also one of the topics that are of great importance in the management of human resources.

1. Human resources: Importance and challenges. Pre-school education in the human resources of the organization.

Pre-school education in the human resources of the organization, teachers, graduates, and other staff as in the organization consists of all persons. These men, the study of the process of education, teaching and management are important topics that have their place.

The importance of human resources.

The human resources organization is significant for them, you will develop the effective use of organization. Teachers and other staff, organization of the teaching process and the students comfortable with the environment plays an important role in creating and motivation. Also, they guide the organization on a good show of himself, we should say that also important.

The troubles of human resources.

However, also the importance of human resources, along with their difficulty. For example, teachers may confront difficulties with pupils studying or tied in with new techniques. While other challenges, the problem of communication between teachers and others, to maintain the level of motivation within the effective implementation of support may come out from problems such as creative or active.

2. Psychological characteristics: Motivation and goals. Psychological characteristics and their role.

Psychological features of man's self-organization, self-management and is important in ensuring efficiency in interactions with others. Their motivation, their goals, identify and resolve conflict in the process of emotions like to work with is registered. These features have great importance in the use of human resources.

Motivation: encourage Staff.

Motivation, encourage their staff to work is one of the main important tools. Staff provide you with a new idea, to set goals related to their own work, and create comfortable working conditions and high cost them to pay attention to the criticism as motivation methods will be effective. Motivated employees, their efficiency, and they feel themselves backed to the organization offered.

Set goals and achieve them.

Setting goals is one of the important tools which help people to work effectively. Defining strategies to achieve the goals of the organization and they made them. Goals, guiding to the

living standards of people to get things done and they should be men should be easy. Goals, teachers and performs the function of a compass that shows the way for others to end.

3. Communications: Part spite adjacent to each other. Types of communication and their importance.

Communication, pre-school education system is not adjacent to participate in important aspects of look at each other. Effective communication, teachers, students and other staff friendly and accuracy of communication between carried out. Types of communication, verbal (language) and nonverbal communication if there is cooperation and their role in the organization plays an important role in achieving the goals.

Effective communication methods

Effective communication method of the reduction of the communication error, the text and the comments in your own time, to provide a clear and friendly manner to participate and thoughts and to give attention to the senses in the lobby. Effective communication, the communication between teachers and others will help you to understand the concepts and goals clearly.

4. Conflict resolution. Higher public: career and team work. Recruitment procedure and decision-making.

Imagine: at your reception asabi expect in the way of your resume, hold tightly, trying to calm the butterflies in your stomach are doing. Chat will work. This can be your dream be created or destroyed, the possibility of access to work is the moment. But have you stopped to think about the other side of the table? Resume sitting in referees lay facing in the collection through a sieve held make difficult decisions?

Hire to work - this is art. This is not only for work, but the team find out about the right fit for issues. Thorough and procedures are working out so decided to accept to work for the company. The onset of the team to successfully choosing the right people they know. So, this to offer you the job look forward to work when referees also find people who can contribute to the success of the team is under pressure to do not forget that.

The importance of team work and community.

"Team work is the dream performs" we have all heard the phrase. And this is true. In the context of today's complex work for the success of cooperation and teamwork is very important. Days have passed and I worked in the silage. Now organizations are united to achieve the overall goal of individuals with different skills, which were emphasised the importance of mutual functional team.

Find more things to be a team player with another language simply means removing. Actively contribute to this knowledge and your own skills, and your colleagues to support and accept diversity. The teams are working well together, they are the incredible things you can obtain. So, you do you become a team member or team leader, and the power of cooperation to remember how that can affect the success of your organization.

5. Organizational development in public.

Organizational culture plays a decisive role in the success of any company. Being in a relationship with each other and with the staff in general defines how the tone of the organization. "Organizational citizenship" to contribute to the overall prosperity of the company and the concept of high staff who work out their requirements and means.

The formation of a strong organizational culture starts from the top. Managers value employees themselves caring environment to contribute to their support and they should

encourage ideas create. This transparent communication, and employee recognition programs can be done through growth and development opportunities. Imagine the sense of purpose and appropriate and staff feel they have spending power will contribute to the success of the organization.

6. Stress management: Resources, provide stability.

Stress. Most of us put this to the general sigh of the word. Now with the fast pace of stress in the developing world, especially in the work place has become an inevitable part of life. But this is how we can have a big impact on our well being and our productivity stress management.

Effective management of stress is healthy, it is very important to maintain a balance work and life. This is to recognize the signs of stress, strategies to reduce its impact and implementation of the facility to seek help when needed. Thus, a regular break to make it up carefully and physical activity as simple or meditation to deal with operations. Create a work environment supportive of work life balance and providing for the organization and employees to help provide resources for stress management is also important.

Remember, stress is inevitable, but how we react to it in our control. So, take a deep breath, away from the table for a moment and get to your mental and emotional well-being, put it in the first place. After all, it is rich in valuable to any organization employees happy and healthy. Pre-school education institutions in the management of human resources and explain about the features of the use of psychological creates the opportunity to express an independent opinion. To achieve success in the management of human resources motivation will increase, and the development of communication abilities, improving stress management and creative to ensure it is the basis of a guarantee. This analysis, pre-school education and national organizations to manage human resources management offers additional knowledge and skills that will help you put in effective way.

SUMMARY

This psychological feature of pre-school education of human resources in organizations and methods will help ensure the effective use effective. Leaders and staff to pay attention to this feature and encourage them to work through the development of advanced in achieving the organization's goals will be successful.

This important point to pay attention to pre-school education, and psychological qualities of the use of human resources in organizations needs to learn can develop. Leaders, staff development, motivatsiyalash, have aspirations to work effectively on the basis of communication and support.

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